

INFLUENCE OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON ACCESS TO INCLUSIVE EDUCATION AND HEALTH OF CHILDREN WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENT IN NASARAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic drastically affected and changed the behavioural patterns of people around the globe, essentially influencing the lives of children who are affected by disabilities, including those with hearing impairments. This study aimed to investigate the influence of the COVID-19 pandemic on access to inclusive education for children with hearing impairments in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Three specific objectives were raised to guide the study, and three research questions were employed to address the research problems. The descriptive research design was used in the study. The target population for the study consisted of thirty (30) children with hearing impairments in Nasarawa State. Twenty (20) respondents were used as the sample population in the study. Structured questionnaires were used as instruments for data collection, and the research was found to be valid and reliable. The mean and standard deviation were employed as statistical techniques in the study. The findings revealed that COVID-19 affected the continuity of inclusive education services for children with hearing impairments in Nasarawa State, remote learning lacks accommodations for hearing-impaired children. The results in Table 2 showed that children with impairments faced challenges in accessing basic healthcare services and information on the COVID-19 pandemic. The lockdown reduces crucial interaction with colleagues and teachers, limiting the potential input for learning. The result also showed that certain measures can be taken to improve the resilience and responsiveness of inclusive education and health care services for children with hearing impairments and those with other disabilities. Five (5) recommendations were made in the study.

Keywords: COVID-19 pandemic; Behavioural patterns; Children with disabilities; Hearing impairment; Inclusive education

Background to the Study

The Chinese government declared the COVID-19 outbreak in January 2020. This respiratory illness is brought on by a new beta-corona virus that has since been dubbed SARS-CoV-2. The World Health Organization (WHO) proclaimed COVID-19 to be a pandemic on March 11, 2020 (Hui et al., 2020). Italy and other nations, including Nigeria, implemented a lockdown. The introduction of health-protective measures like social distancing, regular hand washing, and the use of face masks, together with risk mitigation measures against the spread of COVID-19, were prioritized soon after the disease's

identification, treatment, and isolation (Bubbico et al., 2021). Social constraints to prevent the transmission of COVID-19 viruses became essential in people's daily lives, jeopardizing interpersonal physical interactions and communication within the community. Because of people's fear of contracting COVID-19 and the epidemic's unpredictability, the global populace was greatly impacted emotionally. Populations affected by the HINI influenza, MERS-CoV, and Ebola epidemics have already experienced psychological distress, including anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorders (Shultz et al., 2014). Since children with hearing impairments are also an integral part of society, these experiences have also influenced them.

Hearing impairment is a term used to describe all categories of hearing problems ranging from mild, moderate, and severe to profound conditions. It is defective hearing, absence from normal hearing, and lack of linguistic information. According to Jerry (2023), Children with hearing impairment are those who find it difficult to process linguistic information through audition, with or without the use of hearing aids. The World Health Organization (2021) observed that disabling hearing is one of the major public health problems around the globe that keeps increasing daily due to wrong medication, ignorance, delayed medical intervention, and carelessness on the part of parents or caregivers. Hence, hearing impairment as a disability added more problems to individuals with hearing impairment during COVID-19 because of the lack of access to relevant information and knowledge about the deadly Coronavirus.

United Nations (2020) reports that the psychological effects of COVID-19 became worse than the disease's physical effects. In the UK, for example, the number of patients experiencing mental health issues rose by around 50% when the nation was under lockdown (Daly et al., 2020). In addition, sleep disturbances became one of the primary health issues linked to the COVID-19 outbreak, rising by 57.1% in Italy during the nation's lockdown (Casagrande et al., 2020).

Comparatively, to the general population, people with hearing impairments and those with other disabilities face more challenges to social care, education, and effective communication, as well as lower educational attainment and unemployment rates (World Health Organization, 2020; Rotarou et al., 2021). Furthermore, it was revealed that children in Nigeria including Nasarawa state who had hearing impairments brought on by disabilities or pre-existing diseases experienced much higher psychological discomfort related to COVID-19. To incorporate children and youth with hearing impairments and other disabilities into an inclusive school system, it is critical to concentrate on their educational requirements while the COVID-19 Pandemic wreaks havoc over the globe.

An educational strategy known as inclusive education gives students more chances to succeed academically and socially while also giving them a sense of community membership. Every student should have a sense of belonging and have their individual needs and learning met through inclusive education. An inclusive education program accepts students from all backgrounds, including those with disabilities. The goal of inclusive education is to guarantee that both children without disabilities and those with hearing impairments have access to the knowledge and skills necessary to become self-sufficient and contributing members of their communities. The COVID-19 epidemic makes education harder since schools have to accommodate students with a wider range of backgrounds and skill levels. Over 25 million people with disabilities, including those who are hearing impaired in Nigeria are disproportionately affected by barriers to the implementation of basic preventive measures, such as

difficulty in washing hands, maintaining social distancing, difficulty in accessing public health information, institutional barriers that are replicated during the COVID-19 crisis, and hygiene concerns. (World Health Organization). Children with hearing impairment mode of communication are visually oriented thus, they find it difficult to keep social distance.

Due to inadequate professionals in special education and the ignorance of parents or caregivers in meeting their needs, the COVID-19 pandemic has put the education of children with hearing impairment in jeopardy. As a result, there is a chance that these children will lose out on learning opportunities and inclusion both during and after the pandemic. Remote homeschooling for children with hearing impairments necessitates not only having access to sufficient resources, the internet, books, and other educational materials but also having access to particular assistive devices that enable a continuous education at home and meet the child's unique learning needs (UNICEF, 2020). It is critical to address the educational needs of children with hearing impairment and other challenges during the COVID-19 Pandemic, which is almost over. According to the World Health Organization (2020), communication obstacles increase a person's vulnerability in Nigeria including Nasarawa State, Disabilities affect one billion people globally by preventing them from obtaining adequate health and social care, habilitation, and rehabilitation services. Through the creation of treaties like the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (1975), and the World Program of Action concerning disabled persons (1982), adopted by the United Nations, and currently, Nigeria has established the National Commission for Persons with Disabilities with similar trend in some states of the country, there has been some struggle over the years to abolish discrimination and non-inclusion of children with hearing impairment and other disabilities.

The World Health Organization declared COVID-19 a public health emergency of major concern at the end of January 2020. To stop the virus's spread, several health officials then announced instructions to stay at home and implemented other preventative measures. Although the pandemic had a significant negative influence on people's psychological and physical well-being and their ability to access school, people with disabilities including those who have hearing impairments need extra care to meet their communication needs and remain healthy (Wheeler et al., 2009). In this regard, the majority of children with hearing loss experience difficulties in communication. In this regard, most children with hearing impairment were faced with communication and information challenges. Strategies for ensuring access to education and health opportunities remain a source of concern. This study highlights the influence of the COVID-19 pandemic on access to Inclusive Education and the health of children with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Statement of the problem

Adoption and implementation of inclusive education in Nigeria improved the practices of inclusion until 2020 when the coronavirus was announced around the globe and it became a threat to the capacity to assess health, social care, rehabilitation services, and communication barriers that make children with hearing impairment and those with other disabilities more vulnerable. They find it difficult to cope with education due to the lack of accessible information on the corona virus as most of the support services were not provided by the government, for example, sign language interpreters, hearing rehabilitation services, and relevant equipment used in rehabilitation of hearing process during the covid-19 briefing. Access to inclusive education, hearing care services, healthcare and social services, and communication

services were neglected due to the influence of covid-19 pandemic in Nigeria especially in Nasarawa state.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to explore the influence of the COVID-19 pandemic on access to Inclusive Education and the health of children with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. assess the extent of disruption to inclusive education services for children with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic.
2. examine the influence of the COVID-19 pandemic on the availability and accessibility of healthcare services for children with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State.
3. provide strategies for improving the resilience and responsiveness of inclusive education and healthcare systems for children with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State in response to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Research Questions

1. To what extent has the COVID-19 pandemic affected the continuity of inclusive education services for children with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State?
2. What are the challenges faced by children with hearing impairment in accessing healthcare services during the COVID-19 pandemic in Nasarawa State?
3. What are the strategies that can be employed to improve the resilience and responsiveness of inclusive education and healthcare systems for children with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State in response to the COVID-19 pandemic?

Methodology

The descriptive survey design was used in the investigation. The design was chosen by Afolabi (2000) and Adetoro (2003), who clarified that a descriptive survey design could be employed in a study where data is derived from a questionnaire intended to capture present conditions or opinions of a community. These citations led the researcher to conclude that the survey approach was acceptable for this study because it needs respondent data to make population-wide generalizations.

Thirty (30) Nasarawa State residents with hearing impairments were the study's target demographic. The sample size was twenty (20) respondents with hearing impairments. The twenty (20) respondents with hearing impairments were chosen using a systematic random sampling technique. A structured questionnaire was the study's instrument. The questionnaire's items were arranged in line with the research questions that were developed to direct the investigation. The questionnaire was created using simple language and distributed to professionals in the fields of special education and health needs. This led to the conclusion that the instrument was legitimate and trustworthy for the study. Cronbach alpha reliability method was used to determine the internal consistency of the questionnaire items. A pilot test was conducted only on 5 persons with hearing impairment. A reliability coefficient of 0.82 was obtained. Standard deviation and arithmetic mean statistics were used to analyze the data that was gathered. Strongly agree (SA, 4), agree (A, 3), disagree (D, 2), and strongly disagree (SD, 1) were the tabulated results of the questionnaire. Items in the questionnaire with a mean score of 2.5 or higher were accepted, while those with a score of less than 2.5 were disregarded. This methodology was used to guide the decision-making process regarding the findings.

Results

The data analysis summary for each of the research questions is displayed in the tables below.

Research Question 1

How has the COVID-19 pandemic affected the continuity of inclusive education services for children with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State?

Table 1: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation of Respondents Rating on how the COVID-19 pandemic affected the continuity of inclusive education services for children with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State

S/N	Items	X	Std Dev	Decision
1	School closures during COVID-19 disrupted inclusive education services for children with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State.	2.72	1.3658	Accepted
2	Remote learning lacked accommodations for hearing-impaired children, hindering their engagement.	2.73	1.3882	Accepted
3	Children missed face-to-face interaction with educators and peers, impacting social development.	3.0	1.4062	Accepted
4	Adequate access to assistive technologies affected the learning of children with hearing impairment during the pandemic.	1.9	0.74	Rejected
5	Parents faced challenges in providing adequate support and guidance for remote learning of their children with hearing impairment.	2.73	1.3882	Accepted
6	The limited availability of online learning tools and sign language interpreters affected the learning of children with hearing impairment.	3.06	1.5164	Accepted
7	The closure of specialized institutions created barriers to accessing tailored educational support.	2.68	1.3754	Accepted

The information in Table 1 displayed the respondents' mean evaluations of their answers to 20 questions about how the COVID-19 epidemic influenced Nasarawa State's inclusive education services for children with hearing impairments. The true limit for one of the items was less than the 2.5 cut-off point. This suggests that all except one of the things were agreed upon by the responders.

Research Question 2

What are the challenges faced by children with hearing impairment in accessing healthcare services during the COVID-19 pandemic in Nasarawa State?

Table 2: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation of Respondents Rating on the challenges faced by children with hearing impairment in accessing healthcare services during the COVID-19 pandemic

S/N	Items	X	Std Dev	Decision
1	Limited access to sign language interpreters for communication	3.19	1.489	Agree
2	Difficulty in understanding healthcare information due to masks obscuring lip reading.	2.77	1.3777	Agree
3	Transportation barriers to reach healthcare facilities.	2.69	1.2548	Agree
4	Reduced availability of educational materials about COVID-19 in sign language	3.12	1.3611	Agree
5	Fear and anxiety about visiting healthcare facilities due to unfamiliarity with safety protocols	2.64	1.2414	Agree
6	Increased risk of medical neglect and delayed treatment due to communication barriers	2.68	1.3754	Agree
7	Limited availability of healthcare professionals trained in communicating with hearing-impaired individuals.	2.75	1.4127	Agree

All of the elevated items were scored higher than the 2.5 cut-off threshold, as Table 2 demonstrates. This indicates that every respondent believed that the issues listed above were some of the barriers that children with hearing loss encountered when trying to get healthcare services in Nasarawa State during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Research Question 3

What are the strategies that can be employed to improve the resilience and responsiveness of inclusive education and healthcare systems for children with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State in response to the COVID-19 pandemic?

Table 3: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation of Respondents Rating Respondents on the strategies that can be employed to improve the resilience and responsiveness of inclusive education and healthcare systems for children with hearing impairment in response to the COVID-19 pandemic

S/N	Items	X	Std Dev
1	Develop accessible online learning platforms with sign language interpreters.	3.06	1.5164
2	Provide training for teachers and healthcare professionals on inclusive practices	2.68	1.3754
3	Establish helplines for guidance and support for children with hearing impairment	2.75	1.4127
4	Provide financial support for families covering the costs of education and healthcare.	2.97	1.4946
5	Advocate for policy changes to prioritize inclusion.	3.12	1.3611
6	Ensure availability and maintenance of assistive devices for children with hearing impairment.	2.72	1.3658
7	Integrate sign language and deaf culture education into school curricula.	2.73	1.3882

As can be seen in Table 3, every item that was raised received a rating higher than the 2.5 threshold. This suggests that, in response to the COVID-19 proposal, every respondent agreed that every action listed would unquestionably increase the responsiveness and resilience of inclusive healthcare and education systems for children with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State.

Discussion

The findings of this study as presented in Table 1 revealed how the COVID-19 pandemic affected the continuity of inclusive education services for children with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State. School closures during COVID-19 disrupted inclusive education services for children with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State. Remote learning lacked accommodations for hearing-impaired children, hindering their engagement. Also, children with hearing impairment missed face-to-face interaction with educators and peers, impacting social development. This is consistent with the assertion made by Obi and Okoro (2021) that students with hearing impairments were less productive when they worked remotely and were alone. Hearing-impaired students believe that learning requires face-to-face interaction. The lockdown limited opportunities for important interactions with professors and coworkers, which limited their ability to contribute to their learning. Some only miss their buddies and their school. A student's sense of isolation was heightened by the suddenly deserted streets and public transit since mobility was limited but not entirely stopped.

The result also showed that children with hearing impairment encountered several challenges accessing healthcare services during the COVID-19 pandemic in Nasarawa State. Children with hearing impairment during the pandemic have Limited access to sign language interpreters for communication, difficulty in understanding healthcare information due to masks obscuring lip reading, reduced availability of educational materials about COVID-19 in sign language, and many others. Oluwaseun and Ogunyemi (2020) supported that the prolonged isolation and disruption to daily routines caused by the COVID-19 pandemic affected the mental health and psychosocial well-being of children with hearing impairment. Social distancing measures, school closures, and limitations on social gatherings reduced opportunities for peer interaction, extracurricular activities, and participation in community events, which are crucial for fostering social skills, self-esteem, and emotional resilience among these students.

The study further reveals that certain measures can be taken to improve the resilience and responsiveness of inclusive education and healthcare systems for children with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State in response to the COVID-19 pandemic such as developing accessible online learning platforms with sign language interpreters, providing training for teachers and healthcare professionals on inclusive practices, establishing helplines for guidance and support for children with hearing impairment and many others.

Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic has posed significant challenges to access to inclusive education and health services for children with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State. Disrupted education, limited access to healthcare, increased social isolation, and exacerbated inequalities have impacted the well-being and development of these children. As we navigate the post-pandemic landscape, concerted efforts are needed to address these challenges and ensure the inclusion and well-being of children with hearing impairment.

Recommendations

1. Policymakers in Nigeria should develop and implement inclusive policies that prioritize the needs of children with hearing impairment in the education and healthcare sectors.
2. The government should improve access to online learning platforms with specialized features for hearing-impaired students, such as closed captioning and sign language interpretation.
3. The government should allocate sufficient resources to support the implementation of inclusive education and healthcare services, including assistive technologies and specialized training for professionals.
4. The Health Sectors in Nasarawa State need to strengthen their healthcare services to ensure continued access to healthcare for children with hearing impairment, including routine check-ups, therapy sessions, and access to hearing aids or cochlear implants.
5. The government should implement inclusive education practices that accommodate the diverse needs of children with hearing impairment, including providing specialized support services, accessible learning materials, and assistive technologies.

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